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INTELLECTUAL CONTROL SYSTEMS AND METROLOGICAL SUPPLY OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Abstract: *Scientific and technical progress makes great demands for quality of engineering production. The priority is to ensure metalworking equipment with required dimensional accuracy during the entire period of operation at minimum manufacturing costs. In article considered the problem of increasing of accuracy of processing products on CNC. The authors offers a solution to the problem by providing compensating adjustment in the trajectory of the cutting tool and machining mode. The necessity of creation of mathematical models of processes behavior in an automated technological system operations (OATS). Based on the research, authors have proposed a generalized diagram of diagnosis and input operative correction and approximate mathematical models of individual processes of diagnosis.*

Keywords: *metrological supply, product quality, intelligent measuring instruments, metrological control, automation of technological processes, calibration procedures, standards, international certification organizations*

ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЦЕССОВ

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Аннотация: *Научно-технический прогресс предъявляет высокие требования к качеству машиностроительной продукции. Приоритетной задачей является обеспечение металлообрабатывающего оборудования необходимой размерной точности в течение всего периода эксплуатации при минимальных затратах на изготовление. В статье рассмотрена проблема повышения точности обработки изделий на станках с ЧПУ. Авторы предлагают решение проблемы путем обеспечения компенсирующей регулировки траектории движения режущего инструмента и режима обработки. Обоснована необходимость создания математических моделей поведения процессов в автоматизированной технологической системе (АТС). На основе исследования авторами предложены обобщенная схема диагностики и ввода оперативной коррекции, а также приближенные математические модели отдельных процессов диагностики.*

Ключевые слова: *метрологическое обеспечение, качество продукции, интеллектуальные средства измерений, метрологический контроль, автоматизация технологических процессов, процедуры калибровки, стандарты, международные сертификационные организации.*

Introduction. We can talk about the crisis in the metal working industry, having regard to the present state of the global economy, which is in shambles. The enterprises of engineering branch are faced the problem of reduction of production costs. Under such conditions, absence of possibility attracting additional capital becomes impossibility of performing logistical reequipment, which affects the competitiveness of products. Scientific and technological progress can't be stopped, in fact every year there is an acceleration in the rating of its development. All the new discoveries in fundamental and applied areas of knowledge makes it possible to create a fundamentally new equipment. Manufacturing industry is the last limiting link in a long chain from the scientist to the final consumer. It isn't enough to make a discovery also it is necessary to develop technology of processing of the product received as a result of discovery which is possible for processing on the available equipment. At this stage of historical development the leading role in manufacturing industry is played by metal working. Therefore, rates of development of scientific and technical progress, finally, depend on a level of development of opportunities of metal-working industry. The basis of metal-working industry is cutting process. Realization of this process allows to receive everything that variety of vehicles and machinery which so simplify our life. Process of cutting of metals, despite nearly one and a half centenary history of studying, remains misunderstood. And it definitely imposes restrictions on possibility of production of the set quality with the minimum material expenses. During an era of competitive struggle between the separate enterprises of engineering branch, advantages are got by the one who is capable to use most effectively resources of the available processing equipment for release of high-quality production. Possibly to achieve the solution of this production task due to increase of effective management of cutting process. There are various approaches to increase of effective management of processing on the metal-cutting equipment. Early studies and the first discoveries in this branch of knowledge were made in the 50th years of the XX century, along with emergence of the first systems of the computer numerical control (CNC). It is necessary to tell that emergence of CTC systems led to emergence of interest in this area. At the beginning increase of effective management of process of cutting was reduced to stabilization of separate output parameters. Was considered, for example, that the technological system will work most effectively if forces of cutting will remain constants in time.

Methods. Development of CTC systems went on the way of complication of process of management of movement of executive bodies – from position

systems to planimetric that, finally, resulted in insufficient efficiency of approach of the management of processing based on stabilization of forces of cutting. In this regard adaptive control systems of processing arose and began to develop. Such systems trace a condition of processing equipment in processing and to a campaign of different detection of errors introduce amendments in the operating trajectory (OT) of movement of executive workers of bodies and the modes of processing. It is necessary to notice that in processing there is a set of various errors.

Results. All variety of errors can be reduced to the following reasons:

1. – wear of the rubbing surfaces of processing equipment;
2. – change of spatial situation and a geometrical form of elements of processing equipment, under the influence of the efforts arising in the course of cutting;
3. – change of spatial situation and a geometrical form of elements of processing equipment, under the influence of thermal deformations;
4. – wear of an edge of the cutting tool in processing;
5. – errors of production and assembly of elements, processing equipment;
6. – unforeseen refusals, both separate knots, and processing equipment in general.

All these phenomena arising in technological system doesn't work separately. They works closely intertwining, mutually make an impact at each other thus on the final accuracy of processing. At this stage of development of science and equipment management of processing on CNC machines, it is carried out by means of intellectual systems of adaptive control, i.e. systems controlling technological parameters of system in the course of its work.

Nowadays, there is an opinion that the most adequate components of control systems for high intelligent functions are Intelligent Elements based on knowledge. Therefore, these Intelligent Elements are reasonably put into use as basic prototypes of modern AI systems. For examples, the information processing with the help of logical means allows to obtain some preferences with acceptable control solutions, and thus promote to find the most successful control outcomes. As the main mechanisms of intellectualization in such systems, the following reasoning mechanisms are usually employed: productive rule, “If condition is satisfied, then do something”; fuzzy rule, “much, little, ...”; logical programming; deductive reasoning; automated theorem proving; automated hypothesis generation; analogical reasoning; object-oriented methods. The classification of

mechanisms for Knowledge-based Systems are presented above. Moreover, several mechanisms presented from similar classes usually are combined together to use. What's more, the Knowledge-based systems using object-logical languages, frame-based logics and logical programming are also considered as popular classes of Intelligent Systems nowadays. However, the most popular practical application in the area of Intelligent Systems are recognized as Dynamic Expert Systems which could be reasonably called as prototypes of modern Intelligent Control Systems.

Discussion. By applying Intelligent Systems that possess complicated multi-level architectures, such as control systems of flight vehicles, it becomes more and more possible to realize the synergistic effect, i.e. increasing efficiency by utilizing mutual correlation and mutual intensification among various kinds of activities. During the modernization and development process of connections between functional systems, it is highly necessary to build and improve the mutualism of functional systems. Besides, symbiosis of subsystems should be mutual beneficial, and thus, optimization of such functional systems interactions is a complex problem. In general, to solve this complex problem multi-criteria optimization are suggested to put into use. Hence, the state parameters of each subsystem and the whole Intelligent Systems, as well as parameters that characterize the efficiency of connections between these subsystems would be optimized. Therefore, the maximization of positive interactions between all the subsystems of Intelligent Systems can be reached and the establishment of mutualism of all subsystems might thus be realized.

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